

Table S8: Summary of the three best species delimitation models obtained from the four BPP analyses with different prior setting on ancestral population size and divergence times (BPP1–4) (see methods section for details).

Order of Ancestral Nodes	Model	No. Spp.	Posterior			
			BPP1	BPP2	BPP3	BPP4
1. TH, Tsp4, Tsp5, Tsp2, Tsp3, TS, TS 1, TR, TT, TT1, Tsp1		10				
2. TH, Tsp4, Tsp5, Tsp2, Tsp3, TS, TS 1, TR	1111111011		0.848	0.844	0.637	0.627
3. TH, Tsp4, Tsp5, Tsp2 4. Tsp4, Tsp5, Tsp2 5. Tsp4, Tsp5		11				
6. Tsp3, TS, TS1, TR 7. Tsp3, TS, TS1	1111111111		0.113	0.120	0.363	0.373
8. TS, TS1 9. TT, TT1, Tsp1 10. TT, TT1		9				
	1111011011		0.035	0.031	0.000	0.000